

A revision of the Mediterranean Raphitomidae 1: on the sibling species *Raphitoma contigua* Monterosato, 1884 and *Raphitoma spadiana* n. sp. (Gastropoda, Conoidea)

Revisión de los Raphitomidae del Mediterráneo 1: las especies hermanas *Raphitoma contigua* Monterosato, 1884 y *Raphitoma spadiana* n. sp. (Gastropoda, Conoidea)

Francesco PUSATERI*, Riccardo GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI** and Marco OLIVERIO***

Recibido el 28-V-2011. Aceptado el 26-X-2011

ABSTRACT

A new raphitomid toxoglossan, *Raphitoma spadiana* n. sp., is described from the Mediterranean Sea. It is the sister species to *R. contigua* Monterosato, 1884, from which it differs in the different protoconch (paucispiral vs. multiespiral), adding to a long list of pairs of caenogastropod species differing in their larval development.

RESUMEN

Una nueva especie de toxogloso rafitómido, *Raphitoma spadiana* n. sp., se describe del Mediterráneo. Es especie hermana de *R. contigua* Monterosato, 1884, de la cual se diferencia por su protoconcha (pauciespiral vs. multiespiral), y se añade a una larga lista de parejas de especies que difieren en su desarrollo larvario (planctotrófico vs. no-planctotrófico).

INTRODUCTION

The superfamily Conoidea, with over 300 genera and 4.000 recognised species, but probably over 12,000 extant species (BOUCHET, 1990; TAYLOR, KANTOR & SYSOEV, 1993; TUCKER, 2004), represents the largest radiation of the entire phylum Mollusca. In a work on the phylogeny of the group based on a cladistic analysis of foregut morphology, TAYLOR *ET AL.* (1993) have highlighted the rampant homoplasy in the characters of shell and radula in conoideans. Accordingly, they have rearranged most of the conoideans into two families:

Conidae, comprising Coninae and 4 subfamilies traditionally considered as 'turrids', and Turridae s.s. including some of the traditional 'turrids'. More recently, PULLANDRE, SAMADI, BOISSE-LIER, SYSOEV, KANTOR, CRUAUD, COULOUX & BOUCHET (2008) and BOUCHET, KANTOR, SYSOEV & PULLANDRE (2011), based on DNA phylogeny, have provided a major update of conoidean classification. Although a larger taxonomic coverage would be desirable to further stabilize the molecular phylogeny, however, the position of

*Via Castellana, 64 - 90135 Palermo. E-mail: francesco@pusateri.it

** Via Mater Dolorosa, 54 - 90146 Palermo. E-mail: malakos@tin.it

*** Dept. Biology and Biotechnologies "Charles Darwin". Zoology, Viale dell'Università 32, I-00185 Roma. E-mail: marco.oliverio@uniroma1.it

the Raphitomidae as a clade of the Conoidea is sufficiently supported.

Raphitomidae are based on the genus *Raphitoma*, which was introduced by BELLARDI, (1847: 85), as including 34 fossil and extant species. During the revision of the Mediterranean Raphitomidae we are currently carrying out, we have found several pairs of species, differing only or mostly in the size and shape of the protoconch. After the pioneer works of THORSON (1946, 1950), addressing the relationships between protoconch morphology and type of larval development in the caenogastropods, the dichotomy multispiral protoconch/planktotrophic development vs. paucispiral protoconch/lecithotrophic development has been largely accepted (JABLONSKI & LUTZ, 1980; REX & WARÉN, 1982). Although some authors have used this dichotomy to allocate species into planktotrophic vs. non-planktotrophic genera (e.g.: POWELL, 1966; AARTSEN 1988), BOUCHET (1990) has clearly demonstrated that such abuse of protoconch morphology would produce polyphyletic taxa, and artificially separate closely related species among distinct genera. In raphitomid, the separation of *Raphitoma* (multispiral protoconch) and *Philbertia* (paucispiral protoconch) is inconsistent and must be rejected.

On the other hand, differences in protoconch morphology, which reflect differences in larval development (planktotrophic vs. lecithotrophic) are a good base to recognise distinct species in caenogastropods. In fact, poecilogony (the ability of a species to use different developmental strategies, e.g. planktotrophy and lecithotrophy) is not observed within the prosobranchs (BOUCHET, 1989), whilst it has been sometimes recorded among opisthobranchs [e.g.: *Haminoea callidegenita* Gibson & Chia,

1989, *Elysia chlorotica* Gould, 1870, *Alderia willowi* Krug, Ellingson, Burton & Valdés, 2007 (WEST, HARRIGAN & PIERCE 1984, GIBSON & CHIA, 1995, KRUG, ELLINGSON, BURTON & VALDÉS, 2007)].

The presence of pairs of caenogastropod species with multispiral vs. paucispiral protoconchs has been particularly reviewed in the Mediterranean Sea (see OLIVERIO, 1996a, b, with references therein), but it is a phenomenon observed on a global scale (OLIVERIO, 1997). It has been related to a speciation model, where the very shift in larval development with loss of planktotrophy has been the driving mechanism of speciation (OLIVERIO 1996a).

In the genus *Raphitoma*, we have scored several such pairs of species with different protoconchs (multispiral vs. paucispiral). A thorough revision of all Mediterranean pairs (which we have currently in progress) will be the subject of a forthcoming paper. In the present work we present the case of the rather obscure taxon *Raphitoma contigua* (Monterosato, 1884), of which we have examined the type material and selected a lectotype with multispiral protoconch to stabilize the usage of the name, and its unnamed sister species with paucispiral protoconch.

Abbreviations:

HUJ = Hebrew University of Jerusalem (Israel)
MCZR = Museo Civico di Zoologia di Roma (Italy)
MNHN = Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris, France)
NMW = National Museum of Wales (Cardiff, United Kingdom)
SMNH = Swedish Museum of Natural History (Stockholm, Sweden)
sh = shell(s)

SYSTEMATICS

(Citation of unpublished names is not intended for taxonomic purposes)

Family CONIDAE Fleming, 1822
Subfamily RAPHITOMINAE Bellardi, 1875

Genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847

Type species: *Pleurotoma hystrix* Cristofori and Jan, 1832 (*nomen nudum*, validated by Bellardi, 1847 as "*Pleurotoma hystrix* Jan") by subsequent designation (Monterosato, 1872: 16).

Synonyms:

Homotoma Bellardi, 1875 non Guérin-Ménéville, 1844 – type species: *Murex textile* Brocchi, 1814 by subsequent designation (Fischer, 1883).

Cirillia Monterosato, 1884, non Rondani, 1856 – type species: *Murex linearis* Montagu, 1803, by subsequent designation (Crosse, 1885).

Cordieria Monterosato, 1884 non Roualt, 1848 – type species: *Murex reticulatus* Brochi, 1814, by subsequent designation (Crosse, 1885).

Leufroyia Monterosato, 1884 – Type species: *Pleurotoma leufroyi* Michaud, 1827, by subsequent designation (Crosse, 1885)

Philbertia Monterosato, 1884 – type species: *Pleurotoma philberti* Michaud, 1829 by subsequent designation (Crosse, 1885)

Peratoma Harris & Burrows, 1891 – nomen novum pro *Homotoma* Bellardi, 1875, non Guérin Ménéville, 1844

Cenodagreutes E.H. Smith, 1967 – type species: *Cenodagreutes aethus* E. H. Smith, 1967, by original designation.

Cyrtoides Nordsieck, 1968 – type species: *Pleurotoma rudis* Scacchi, 1836, by original designation.

Lineotoma Nordsieck, 1977 – nomen novum pro *Cirillia* Monterosato, 1884, non Rondani, 1856

Diagnosis: Shell of small to medium-small size (5-25 mm), turreted, fusiform or ovoid-fusiform, with slender spire and uniformly convex whorls. Reticulate-cancellate sculpture on the teleoconch. Protoconch of 3-4 whorls when multispiral, with a protoconch I (embryonic shell) of 0.5-0.7 whorl and a protoconch II (larval shell) of 2-3 whorls, with a diagonally cancellate sculpture. Paucispiral protoconch of 2 whorls, with large nucleus and reticulate sculpture.

Remarks: For the complex nomenclatural issues, including the type

species designations, see DALL (1918), VAN AARTSEN, MENKHORST & GITTENBERGER (1984: 89-90) and ROLÁN, OTERO-SCHMITT & FERNANDES (1998: 105).

In the Mediterranean Sea, species of *Raphitoma* are usually found alive on soft bottoms, ranging from coastal bioclastic sands to muddy bioclastic sands (DC and DE, respectively; PÉRÈS & PICARD, 1964) although it is not infrequent to find specimens hiding under stones and in crevices, especially at daytime.

Raphitoma contigua (Monterosato, 1884) (Figs. 1-3, 14)

Philbertia contigua Monterosato, 1884:133

Type material: Lectotype (here designated, 9.05 x 4.16 mm) and one paralectotype (9.30 x 4.10 mm) with handwritten label by Monterosato: "Ph. contigua typ. Monts! Palermo" (MCZR, 16702/1); 3 paralectotypes with handwritten labels by Monterosato: "Ph. contigua Monts. / Napoli Staz. Zool." (MCZR, 16702/2); 2 paralectotypes labelled "contigua Napoli" (MCZR, 16702/3); 3 paralectotypes with handwritten labels by Monterosato: "R. contigua – Isole Baleari" (MCZR, 16702/4); 16 paralectotypes with handwritten label by Monterosato "Ph. contigua M. / Pal!", coll. Coen in HUIJ, 8072 (including 7 specimens of *R. bicolor*); 2 paralectotypes with handwritten Dautzenberg label: "Clathurella purpurea / Montagu / var. Philberti Michaud / St Lunaire / Types Moll. Rouss. / t. I pl. 14 fig. 13,14" (two specimens of *R. oblonga*) (MNHN, Paris); 1 paralectotype with handwritten Dautzenberg label: "Clathurella purpurea / Montagu / var. Philberti Michaud / Roussillon / Type Moll. Rouss. / t. I pl. 14 fig. 15" (a specimen of *R. atropurpurea*) (MNHN, Paris). Type locality: Palermo.

Figures 1-4. Shells of *Raphitoma* spp. 1-3. *Raphitoma contigua* (Monterosato, 1884). 1a-c: lectotype (MCZR, 16702/1, h: 9.05 mm) with original label; 2: Ficarazzi, Palermo (coll. Pusateri, h: 10 mm); 3: Roquebrune, Les Issambres (coll. Hoarau, h: 9.7 mm), subadult shell with 8 spiral cordlets above the aperture. 4. *Raphitoma lineolata* B.D.D., 1884, St. Raphaël, France (coll. Hoarau, h: 7.2 mm).

Figuras 1-4. Conchas de Raphitoma spp. 1-3. Raphitoma contigua (Monterosato, 1884). 1a-c: lectotipo (MCZR, 16702 / 1, h: 9,05 mm) con la etiqueta original; 2: Ficarazzi, Palermo (col. Pusateri, h: 10 mm); 3: Roquebrune, Les Issambres (col. Hoarau, h: 9,7 mm), concha subadulto con 8 cordoncillos espirales encima de la abertura. 4. Raphitoma lineolata B.D.D., 1884, Saint Raphaël, Francia (col. Hoarau, h: 7,2 mm).

Figures 5-7. Shells of *Raphitoma* spp. figured in Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus (1883), labelled as “*Clathurella purpurea* var. *philberti* Michaud”. 5, 6: *Raphitoma oblonga* (Jeffreys, 1867), St. Lunaire (BDD, 1883: pl. 14, figs 13, 14) with original label (MNHN, Paris); 7: *Raphitoma atropurpurea* (Locard & Caziot, 1899), Roussillon (BDD, 1883: pl. 14 fig. 15) with original label (MNHN, Paris).

Figuras 5-7. Conchas de Raphitoma spp. figuradas en Bucquoy, Dautzenberg y Dollfus (1883), etiquetadas como “Clathurella purpurea var. philberti Michaud”. 5, 6: Raphitoma oblonga (Jeffreys, 1867), Saint Lunaire (BDD, 1883: lám. 14, fig. 13, 14) con la etiqueta original (MNHN, Paris); 7: Raphitoma atropurpurea (Locard y Caziot, 1899), Rosellón (BDD, 1883: lám. 14, fig. 15) con la etiqueta original (MNHN, Paris).

Material examined: The type material and: France–Marseille (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, inv. 16811, 4 sh.: labelled by Monterosato “*H. conformis*”, an unpublished manuscript name). Roquebrune, Les Issambres (Var), (coll. Hoarau, 1 sh.). St. Raphael, Cote d’Azur (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, 16696, 1 sh.: labelled “*P. tomentosa*”). Corsica– Bastia (coll. Pusateri, 1 sh.; coll. Margelli, 1 sh.). Bastia, Alistro (coll. Margelli, 2 sh.). Sardinia–Ennio Falco Cave, Porto Conte, Sassari (coll. Oliverio, 3 sh.). La Maddalena Is. (coll. Rufini, 1 sh.; coll. Spanu, 1 sh.). Oristano, (coll. Rufini, 2 sh.). S’Archittu, Oristano (coll. Sossu, 2 sh.). Stintino, Sassari (coll. Rufini, 1 sh.). Torre del Bollo, Alghero (coll. Spanu, 1 es.). Liguria–Genova (coll. Pusateri 2 sh.). Tuscany–Calambrone (Pisa), coll. Bartolini, 1 sh. Castiglioneccello, Livorno (coll. Coppini, 1 sh.), (coll. Margelli, 2 sh.). Punta Ala, Grosseto (coll. Coppini, 1 sh.). Giannutri Is. (coll. Smriglio, 1 sh.). Elba Is., Marina di Campo (coll. Bartolini, 7 sh.). Elba Is. (coll. Bartolini, 4 sh.). Tuscan Archipelago (coll. Bartolini, 4 sh.). Latium–Tor Paterno Marine Protected Area, Roma (coll. Oliverio, 1 sh.), (coll. Rufini ex Ruggeri, 1 sh.). Campania–Trombetta Cave, -35 m, Palinuro, Salerno (coll. Oliverio, 1 sh.). Punta Campanella, Napoli (coll. Bartolini, 2 sh.). Sicily–Acitrezza, Catania (SMNH, lot 73198F, 10 sh.). Cannizzaro, Catania (coll. Micali, 3 sh.). Palermo (coll. Pusateri, 18 sh., 1 albinistic). Palermo (HUJ, ln. 8080 with Coen’s label *Philbertia purpurea lineolata* BDD, 1 sh.). Aspra, Palermo (coll. Girgenti, 3 sh.). Isola delle Femmine, Palermo (coll. Pusateri, 3 sh. legit Bagnera). Palermo (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, inv. N, 16702, 2 sh.). Gulf of Carini, Palermo (coll. Palmeri, 3 sh.). Capo Passero (coll. Margelli, 1 sh.). Taormina, Messina (coll. Villari, 1 sh.). Pantelleria Is. (coll. Bartolini, 1 sh.). Apulia–Taranto (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, *sine numero*

3 sh.). Croazia – Korcula Is. (coll. Micali, 1 sh.). Krk Is. (coll. Bartolini, 10+ sh.). Velirat, Dugi Otok (Isola Lunga) (coll. Pusateri, 1 sh.). Algeria – Algiers (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, 16815, 1 sh.). “C. d’Afr.” [Coasts of Africa], (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, unnumbered lot, *sine nomine*, 4 sh.).

Description: Shell sub-fusiform (mean h/d 2.2, std 0.13), height 9-15 mm (mean 10.9, std 1.70), width 4.5-6 mm (mean 4.9, std 0.49). Protoconch multispiral of 2.7 convex whorls, height 325 μm , width 300 μm ; protoconch I of 0.6 whorls, width 170 μm , with irregularly placed small tubercles; protoconch II of 2.1 whorls, with a diagonally cancellate sculpture, and two suprasutural small spiral threads.

Teleoconch of 7 convex whorls. Axial sculpture of 16-18 orthocone or slightly opisthocline ribs (sometimes more in larger specimens), and interspaces wider ($\times 1.5$) than the ribs. Spiral sculpture on the last whorl of 17-20 cordlets, of which 6-7 (rarely 8) above the aperture, slightly narrower than the axial ribs. Cancellation rectangular, with small and elongated tubercles at the intersection of axials and spirals. Tubercles on the two adapical cordlets narrow and spinulose (especially in fresh or subadult specimens). Sculpture visible in transparency throughout the internal shell wall.

Subsutural ramp narrow, with small tubercles in correspondence with the axial ribs tip.

Columella simple, slightly sinuous anteriorly, gently angled posteriorly. Outer lip with 8-9 strong inner denticles (rarely 10-11), the most anterior delimiting the siphonal canal, the most posterior delimiting the anal sinus.

Colour uniformly tawny, rarely darker, sometimes with lighter spots. Suprasutural cordlet occasionally white. Occasional comma-shaped white spots on the subsutural ramp.

Distribution: Only known from examined material, probably the entire Mediterranean Sea.

Remarks: MONTEROSATO (1884: 133) introduced *Philbertia contigua* without any description, but with reference to BDD (1883) as follows:

“*P. contigua*, Monts. (nov. forma)

= *Clathurella purpurea* (non Mtg.) var. *Philberti* (non Mich.), B., D. e D. – l.c.

[Moll. Mar. Roussillon] p. 40, t. 14, f. 13-15 (C. di Prov.).

=? *Anna Massena* Risso – 1826, p. 214, f. 68 (foss. Alpi Marit.).

Isole Baleari (Monjò); Alger (Joly); Bona (Hagenmüller); Palermo e Messina (Monts.); Napoli, Lipari (Tiberi) ecc.”

Evidently, Monterosato did not check *de visu* the original material used for BDD’s plates (now stored at MNHN, Paris: Figs. 5-7), relying only on BDD’s figures. In fact, Monterosato cites “C.[oste] di Prov.[enza]” (coasts of Provence), evidently presuming that the figured specimens were all from Provence. Actually, the specimens in BDD’s figs 13 and 14 (MNHN, Paris) are labelled as coming from St. Lunaire (Bretagne), and only the shell of fig. 15 is from Roussillon. However, the lots in the Monterosato collection labelled as *Philbertia contigua* are not conspecific with the specimens figured in BDD’s figs 13-14 (Figs 5, 6), which are referable to *Raphitoma oblonga* (Jeffreys, 1867) a valid species from the Channel area, nor with the specimen figured in BDD’s fig. 15 (Fig. 7), which is referable to *Raphitoma atropurpurea* (Locard & Caziot, 1899). Monterosato’s concept of *contigua* remained constant, as we have verified in several collections hosting specimens ex Monterosato (Melville-Tomlin, National Museum of Wales, lot 12908; Coen, Hebrew University, lot 8072). Evidently, also DAUTZENBERG & DUROUCHOUX, 1900: 14 and LOCARD & CAZIOT, 1899:58, while citing *R. contigua* realized that the material sent to them by Monterosato did not fit BDD’s figures 13-14, and kept *contigua* as a distinct entity. Nevertheless this does not invalidate that the specific name *contigua* is made nomenclaturally available “by indication” (ICZN art. 12.2), with a type material that includes all the localities cited in MONTEROSATO (1884).

R. contigua (h/d 2.2) is less slender than the most similar species with multispiral protoconch: *R. lineolata* (BDD,

Figures 8-13. Shells of *Raphitoma spadiana* spec. nov. 8a-c: holotype, Lipari Is. (MNHN, h: 9.6 mm); 9, 12: paratype A, Lipari Is. (MNHN, Paris, ex coll. Pusateri h: 8 mm); 10: North African coasts, "C.[oste] d'Afr.[ica]" (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, unnumbered lot, h: 6.8 mm); 11, 13: La Ciotat, France (MCZR, 16773, coll. Monterosato, *sine nomine*, h: 8.6 mm).

Figuras 8-13. Conchas de Raphitoma spadiana spec. nov. 8a-c: holotipo, islas Lipari (MNHN, h: 9,6 mm); 9, 12: paratipo, islas Lipari (MNHN, Paris, ex coll Pusateri h: 8 mm); 10: costas de África del Norte "C.[oste] d'Afr.[ica]." (MCZR, coll Monterosato, lote sin número, h: 6,8 mm); 11, 13: La Ciotat, Francia (MCZR, 16773, col Monterosato, sine nomine, H: 8,6 mm).

Figure 14. *Raphitoma contigua* (Monterosato, 1884). 14a,b: protoconch; 14c: subsutural ramp. Figure 15a-c. Protoconch of *Raphitoma spadiana* n. sp. *Figura 14.* *Raphitoma contigua* (Monterosato, 1884). 14a,b: protoconcha; 14c: rampa subsutural. *Figura 15a-c.* Protoconcha de *Raphitoma spadiana* n. sp.

1882) (h/d 2.8), *R. atropurpurea* (Locard & Caziot, 1899) (h/d 2.8), *R. densa* (Monterosato, 1884) (h/d 2.8), *R. oblonga* (Jeffreys, 1867) (h/d 2.5). *Raphitoma lineolata* (Fig. 4) is very similar in general aspect, but has a less robust shell, lacks the narrow subsutural ramp, has a narrower aperture, and shows always few and scattered white tubercles on the last whorl as well as a subsutural white cord, both lacking in *contigua*. *R. atropurpurea* has a different colour (dark brown-purplish vs. tawny). *R. densa* (Fig. 17) is more densely sculptured, and has a colour pattern of ash-grey spots over a dark chestnut background. *R. oblonga* is a less known, exclusively Atlantic species, differing from *R. contigua* by its narrower aperture and the constant presence of a white spiral line as long as the space of four axial ribs, starting on the outer lip.

R. alternans (Monterosato, 1884) (see Fig. 16) has a paucispiral protoconch,

and differs also from *R. contigua* in being more slender (h/d 2.6 vs. 2.2), and in its colour pattern of white spots over a dark chestnut background.

Shells with identical teleoconchs of the *contigua* type, but with two distinct protoconch types (multispiral vs. paucispiral) are known, and we consider them as distinct species. Therefore, we have examined the protoconchs in the type material of *Philbertia contigua* Monterosato, which turned out to consist as follows: MCZR 16702/1, one shell has a multispiral protoconch, the other lacks protoconch; MCZR 16702/2, one lacks protoconch, two with parts of multispiral protoconch; MCZR 16702/3, both with parts of multispiral protoconch; MCZR 16702/4, with parts of multispiral protoconch. To stabilize the use of the name *R. contigua* we have selected the shell in the lot MCZR, 16702/1 with intact (multispiral) protoconch, as the lectotype of *Philbertia contigua* Monterosato.

Figures 16, 17. Shells of *Raphitoma* spp. 16: *Raphitoma alternans* (Monterosato, 1884), syntype (MCZR, 16676, h: 12.00 mm), Mondello (Palermo); 17: *Raphitoma densa* (Monterosato, 1884), syntype (MCZR, 16807, h: 10.15 mm), Palermo.

Figuras 16, 17. Conchas de Raphitoma spp. 16: Raphitoma alternans (Monterosato, 1884), sintipo (MCZR, 16676, h: 12,00 mm), Mondello (Palermo); 17: Raphitoma densa (Monterosato, 1884), sintipo (MCZR, 16807, h: 10,15 mm), Palermo.

Raphitoma spadiana Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli spec. nov. (Figs. 8-13, 15)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN, Paris) height 9.6 mm, width 4.1 mm, from Lipari Is. (Sicily) (legit Claudio Ebreo). Paratype A (coll. Pusateri, height 8.0 mm, width 3.7), from Lipari Is.; Paratype B (MNHN, Paris) height 8.1 mm, width 3.6 mm, from Scilla, Calabria, -50 m (legit Angelo Vazzana)

Other material examined: France – Marseille (coll. Locard, MNHN Paris, 1 shell). La Ciotat, Cote d’Azur (coll. Monterosato, MCZR, 16773, *sine nomine* 8.6 x 3.8 mm). Sardinia – Alghero (coll. Spanu, 1 sh. juv.). Calabria – Scilla, Reggio Calabria (coll. Vazzana, 20 shells). Sicily – Mondello (Palermo) (coll. Pusateri, 2 shells, juv.). Marettimo Is. (coll. Agamennone 1 shell, juv.). Marettimo Isl. (coll. Agamennone, 1 sh.). Apulia – Taranto (coll. Giannuzzi Savelli, 1 shell). Egypt – Alexandria (coll. Pusateri, legit Claudio Ebreo, 2 shells). Tunisia – Djerba Is., (coll. Agamennone, 1 shell). “C. d’Afr.” [Coasts of Africa], (MCZR, coll. Monterosato, unnumbered lot, *sine nomine* 1 sh. subadult, height 6.8 mm, width 3.2 mm; stored with 4 shells of *R. contigua*). Greece – Crete Is. (coll. Alfinito, 1 shell). Cyprus – (coll. Bartolini, 1 sh.)

Etymology: after our dear friend Gianni Spada, a specialist of turrid taxonomy.

Type locality: Lipari Is.

Description: Shell subfusiform 9.5 mm high and 4.1 mm wide.

Protoconch paucispiral, only protoconch I of 1.25 convex whorls, height 425 μ m, width 450 μ m; sculpture irregularly cancellate.

Teleoconch of 6 convex whorls. Axial sculpture of 18 orthocline ribs, interspaces wider ($\times 1.5$) than the ribs.

Spiral sculpture on the last whorl of 23 cordlets, of which 8 above the aperture, slightly narrower than the axial ribs, interspaces wider ($\times 2$) than the ribs. Cancellation rectangular, with small and elongated tubercles at the intersection of axials and spirals. Tubercles on the two subsutural cordlets

narrow and spinulose. Sculpture visible in transparency throughout the very thin internal shell wall.

Subsutural ramp narrow, with small tubercles in correspondence with the tip of the axial ribs. Two cordlets on the subsutural ramp, the adapical smaller with smaller tubercles, the second being the largest of the spirals. The third cordlet, as small as the first one.

Columella simple, slightly sinuous anteriorly, gently angled posteriorly. Outer lip with 12 strong inner denticles, the most anterior delimiting the siphonal canal, the most posterior delimiting the anal sinus. Denticles 1-2 and 11-12 closer than the others.

Siphonal canal short, open.

Colour uniform light tawny, with rare lighter tubercles. Some axial ribs entirely white on the first three teleoconch whorls; on the last whorl tenth spiral cordlet and last two axial ribs partly white.

Distribution: Only known from examined material, probably entire Mediterranean Sea.

Remarks: Variation of the examined material: height 6.8-11.7 mm (mean 9.4 std 1.76), width 3.2-4.6 mm (mean 4.1 std 0.56); mean h/d: 2.3 std 0.15.

Axial ribs 16-18, sometimes slightly opisthocline in the last whorl. Occasional comma-shaped white spots on the subsutural ramp. Colour ranging from light to very light tawny. White axial ribs from present in all whorls to very rare or absent. The spiral cordlet 10 may be white spotted.

Raphitoma spadiana differs from the closely related *R. contigua* in its paucispiral protoconch and thus an inferred lecithotrophic development (vs. multi-spiral protoconch and an inferred planktotrophic development in *contigua*). Additionally, *R. spadiana* is of slightly smaller size, and lighter in colour. *R. alternans* (Monterosato, 1884) has also a paucispiral protoconch, but differs also from *R. spadiana* by being more slender (h/d 2.6 vs. 2.3), and by its colour pattern of irregular white spots over a dark chestnut background.

R. spadiana (h/d 2.3) is also less slender than the most similar species

with multispiral protoconch: *R. lineolata* (BDD, 1882) (h/d 2.8), *R. atropurpurea* (Locard & Caziot, 1899) (h/d 2.8), *R. densa* (Monterosato, 1884) (h/d 2.8), *R. oblonga* (Jeffreys, 1867) (h/d 2.5).

Raphitoma lineolata (Fig. 4) is very similar in general aspect, but differs in having a less robust shell and a narrower aperture, lacking the narrow subsutural ramp, and showing always few and scattered white tubercles on the last whorl as well as a subsutural white cord, both lacking in *spadiana*. *Raphitoma atropurpurea* has a different colour (dark brown-purplish vs. tawny). *Raphitoma densa* is more densely sculptured, and has a colour pattern of irregular ash-grey spots over a dark chestnut background. *Raphitoma oblonga* is exclusively Atlantic, and differs by its narrower aperture and the constant presence of a white spiral line as long as the space of four axial ribs, starting on the outer lip.

According to the admittedly limited material examined, *R. spadiana* seems to show some interpopulational variation, even over a short geographic scale (which would be congruent with a non-planktotrophic larval development), with at least one extreme case. A lot of 20 adult shells from Scilla (Calabria) range between 5.2-7.8 mm (mean 6.67) in height, and 2.5-3.9 mm (mean 3.16) in width, with h/d 2.11, and are darker than all other examined shells. Given the small number of shells available overall for comparison, we keep this lot within the putative range of *R. spadiana*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Franco Agamennone, Silvia Alfinito, Giuseppe Bagnera, Manrico Coppini, Antonio Girgenti, André Hoarau, Piera Iacopelli, Alessandro Margelli, Paolo Mariottini, Pasquale Micali, Italo Nofroni, Alberto Palmeri, Stefano Rufini, Maria Scaperrotta, Carlo Smriglio, Maurizio Sosso, Maria Teresa Spanu, Angelo Vazzana, Alberto Villari, are thanked for having placed their materials at our disposal, Gianni Repetto for his valuable bibliographic help.

Claudio Manicastro allowed the study of the materials in the Monterosato collection (MCZR, Rome) and Massimo Appolloni and Angela Mastrogiacomo assisted during the visit at MCZR. Philippe Bouchet allowed the study of the materials at MNHN (Paris), and Virginie Heros and Pierre Lozouet assisted during the visit at MNHN. H. Mienis loaned materials from the Coen collection (HUJ, Jerusalem). Anders Warén loaned materials from SMNH

(Stokholm). Stefano Bartolini did the light photographs, SEM photographs were done at the "LIME" (Interdepartmental Laboratory of Electron Micros-

copy) by Andrea Di Giulio, (Dept of Biology, "Roma Tre" University, Rome); digitalization of plates by Floriana Giannuzzi-Savelli.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ARNAUD P.M. 1978 [1977]. Révision des taxa malacologiques méditerranéens introduit par Antoine Risso. *Annales du Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle de Nice*, 5: 101–150
- BELLARDI L. 1847. Monografia delle Pleurotome fossili del Piemonte. *Memorie della Reale Accademia delle Scienze di Torino, serie 2*, 9: 531–650, 4 pls. [according R. Janssen, 1993 the journal issue was published in 1848 but a reprint was distributed in 1847; with proper title and pagination, 119 pp.]
- BOUCHET P. 1989. A review of poecilogony in gastropods. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 55: 67–78
- BOUCHET P. 1990. Turrid genera and mode of development: the use and abuse of protoconch morphology. *Malacologia*, 32 (1): 69–77
- BOUCHET P., KANTOR Y.I., SYSOEV A. & PUILANDRE N. 2011. A new operational classification of the Conoidea. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 77: 273–308.
- CROSSE H. 1885. Nomenclature generica e specifica di alcune Conchiglie Mediterranee, pel marche di Monterosato [book review]. *Journal de Conchyliologie*, 33: 139–142.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & DUROUCHOUX P. 1900. Faune malacologique de Saint-Malo. *Feuille des Jeunes Naturalistes*, 30: 39–62 [not before 9 November 1900].
- FISCHER P. 1880–1887. *Manual de Conchyliologie et de Paléontologie Conchyliologique*. Paris, Savy. pp. xxiv + 1369 p., 23 pl.
- GIBSON G.D. & CHIA F-S, 1995. Developmental variability in the poecilogonous opisthobranch *Haminaea callidegenita*: life-history traits and effects of environmental parameters. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 121: 139–155.
- JABLONSKI D. & LUTZ R. A. 1980. Larval shell morphology: ecological and paleontological applications. In Rhoads D.C. and Lutz R.A. (eds.) *Skeletal growth of aquatic organisms*, Plenum Press, New York, pp. 323–377.
- JANSSEN A.W. 1963. Gastropoda uit de Belgische "Sables de Vieux Jones" en de Nederlandse "Cerithiumklei" (oligoceen). *Basteria*, 27 (3/4): 29–44, pls. 3–4.
- KRUG P.J., ELLINGSON R.A., BURTON R. & VALDÉS Á. 2007. A new poecilogonous species of sea slug (Opisthobranchia: Sacoglossa) from California: comparison with the planktotrophic congener *Alderia modesta* (Lovén, 1844). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 73 (1): 29–38.
- LOCARD A. & CAZIOT E. 1899. Les coquilles marines des côtes de Corse. *Annales de la Société Linnéenne, Lyon*, 46: 246. A reprint of this work was published as separate book with the same title in 1900 by J.B. Baillière et fils, Paris.
- MONTEROSATO T. A. DI 1884. *Nomenclatura generica e specifica di alcune conchiglie mediterranee*. Palermo: Virzi. 152 pp.
- MONTEROSATO T. A. DI 1872. *Notizie intorno alle conchiglie fossili di Monte Pellegrino e Ficarazzi*. Palermo, Ufficio Tipografico di Michele Amenta, 45 pp.
- OLIVERIO M. 1996a. Life-histories, speciation and biodiversity in Mediterranean prosobranchs gastropods. *Vie et Milieu*, 46 (2): 163–169.
- OLIVERIO M. 1996b. Chapter 22. Contrasting developmental strategies and speciation in N.E. prosobranchs: a preliminary analysis. In Taylor J.D. (ed.) *Origin and evolutionary radiation of the Mollusca*, Oxford University Press, pp. 261–266.
- OLIVERIO M. 1997. Global biodiversity and life-history evolution in prosobranchs gastropods. *Iberus*, 16: 73–79.
- PÉRÈS J.M. & PICARD J. 1964. Nouveau manuel de bionomie benthique de la mer Méditerranée. *Recueil des Travaux de la Station Marine d'Endoume*, 31 (47): 3–137.
- PUILANDRE N., SAMADI S., BOISSELIER M-C., SYSOEV A.V., KANTOR YU.I., CRUAUD C., COULOUX C. & BOUCHET P. 2008. Starting to unravel the toxoglossan knot: molecular phylogeny of the "turrids" (Neogastropoda: Conoidea). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 47: 1122–1134.
- REX M. A., & WARÉN A. 1982. Planktotrophic development in deep-sea prosobranch snails from the western North Atlantic. *Deep-Sea Research* part A, 29 (2): 171–184.
- ROLÁN E., OTERO-SCHMITT J. & FERNANDES F. 1998. The family Turridae s.l. in Angola (West Africa), 1: Subfamily Daphnellinae. *Iberus*, 16 (1): 95–118
- TAYLOR J.D. KANTOR YU.I. & SYSOEV A.V. 1993. "Foregut anatomy, feeding mechanisms, relationships and classification of Conoidea (Toxoglossa) (Gastropoda)". *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum, London (Zoology)*, 59: 97–169.

- THORSON G. 1946. Reproduction and larval development of Danish marine bottom invertebrates, with special reference to the planktonic larvae in the Sound (Øresund). *Meddelelser fra Kommissionen for Danmarks Fiskeri- Og Havundersøgelser, Serie: Plankton*, 4: 1–523.
- THORSON G. 1950. Reproductive and larval ecology of marine bottom invertebrates. *Biological Review*, 25: 1–45.
- TUCKER J. K. 2004. Catalog of Recent and fossil turrids (Mollusca: Gastropoda). *Zootaxa*, 682: 1–1295.
- VAN AARTSEN J.J. VAN, MENKHORST H.P. & GITTENBERGER E. 1984. The marine mollusca of the Bay of Algeciras, Spain with general notes on *Mitrella*, Marginellidae and Turridae. *Basteria*, supplement 2: 1–135.
- WEST H.H., HARRIGAN J.F. & PIERCE S.K. 1984. Hybridization of two populations of a marine opisthobranch with different developmental patterns. *The Veliger*, 26 (3): 199–206.